

Employment of Video Learning as an Active Learning Strategy for CBET Curriculum Implementation in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Institutions in Kenya: The Case of Nyandarua National Polytechnic.

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ABSTRACT

This paper explores the extent to which digital technologies and, in particular, video learning has been employed as active learning tools in Competency-Based Education and Training (CBET) curriculum implementation in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions in Kenya. The study was inspired by related studies elsewhere, which point to the challenges of employing more innovative instructional strategies in TVET institutions despite the emphasis on the same. Some studies suggest that the pressure to incorporate new technology in teaching and learning is not always matched with adequate training and support. The introduction of CBET in Kenya has come with the call to apply active learning strategies in its implementation to enhance skills acquisition among technical education trainees, which is its sole principle. The objective of the study was therefore to establish the extent to which these strategies have been employed in the TVET institutions and the factors determining their application. The study was conducted among trainers and trainees at Nyandarua National Polytechnic at the beginning of this year and was descriptive in design. Both qualitative and quantitative approaches were employed for data collection and analysis. Data was collected through questionnaires, which were administered online for the trainees and self-administered for the trainers. The theory of constructivism and the cognitive theory of multimedia learning guided the study. The trainers and trainees were sampled from all nine academic departments in Nyandarua National Polytechnic, where at least one trainer in all departments reported having used video in teaching, a claim that was corroborated by the responses from the trainees. 88% of trainees confirmed to have used video in learning, while 90% of trainers affirmed using video in teaching. These positive observations came amidst myriad challenges that were cited by both trainers and trainees as impeding the use of video learning in the institution. The study thus concluded that significant effort had been made to apply digital technologies as innovative instructional strategies in TVET institutions in Kenya. However, their employment is still engulfed in myriad challenges that need to be addressed to fully realize the benefits of digital instructional strategies, which have been documented, including increasing employability.

Keywords: Digital Technologies; Video Learning; Active Learning Strategies; Curriculum Implementation; TVET Institutions

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital technologies provide a myriad of possibilities for the employment of innovative teaching and learning strategies for Competency-Based Education and Training (CBET) curriculum implementation. CBET emphasizes the use of active learning methodologies to enhance skills acquisition among TVET graduates, and the availability of digital technologies for use in teaching and learning would facilitate this realization. Digital technologies that could be employed in teaching and learning include mobile devices, smartboards, tablets, laptops, simulations, dynamic visualization, and virtual laboratories. Using computers and other digital tools and devices enables students to play a more proactive role and be at the centre of the learning process, which is the goal of active learning. Digital technologies provide learners with many benefits, among them the ability to provide an immediate learning environment with enhanced learner engagement, where the instructor only becomes a guide in the process. Some of the efficiencies that such technologies provide are simply unrivalled by traditional learning methodologies (Haleem, A. et al, 2022).

The use of digital technologies to aid teaching and learning has been supported by a range of studies, among them Puspaningtyas and Ulfa (2020), who state that educators must innovate learning by utilizing technological developments. They maintain that learners will be more motivated to participate in learning activities when using technology-based learning media. According to Priandika et al (2022), the benefits of learning using video, one of the digital technologies that is employable in learning, include increasing student learning motivation, making students happy to learn, replacing teachers in providing material explanations, increasing interest in learning, and improving student learning outcomes. The need to use digital technologies in innovative teaching and learning for CBET curriculum delivery can therefore not be overemphasized. Nevertheless, the use of innovative teaching and learning methodologies in TVET institutions in Kenya has continued to grapple with enormous challenges among them lack of training among trainers in the requisite skills for use of these digital technologies, lack of supportive infrastructure and other relevant resources as alluded to by Wandago, et al, (2017) and Woolfitt (2015).

This paper explores the extent to which video learning has been employed as an active learning tool in Competency-Based Education and Training (CBET) curriculum implementation in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) institutions. The benefits of using video, among other digital technologies to support learning, are numerous. Many empirical studies serve to exemplify these benefits. For instance, video is seen as having advantages for learner engagement in some specific ways, notably in widening participation, emotional engagement, and overall course engagement (Carmichael et al, 2023), which are key tenets for active learning. Video is therefore an important aid in CBET curriculum implementation and delivery, whose main emphasis is learner-centredness and skills acquisition. Video learning has also been proven to increase skills uptake in learners, which is the main objective of CBET to increase employability among TVET graduates. Findings from various research confirm this, as espoused in this paper.

1.1 Problem Statement

Trainers and trainees in TVET institutions in Kenya have adopted active learning strategies for the delivery of the new CBET curriculum, which is still in its early stages of implementation since its rollout three years ago. However, the employment of some of these strategies has faced challenges such as a lack of the requisite resources and infrastructure in the TVET institutions. An instance of this is the use of video learning in TVET institutions, which, despite the documentation of its enormous benefits and despite its being embraced by trainers and trainees in TVET institutions, myriad challenges impede its application. This hinders the full realization of the benefits that stem from video learning as an active learning strategy, among them enhanced skills acquisition for employability.

1.2 Objective

The main objective was to establish the extent to which video learning, a digital technology, has been employed as an active learning strategy in TVET institutions in Kenya, specifically Nyandarua National Polytechnic.

Specific objectives were to:

1. Establish if video learning has been employed in Nyandarua National Polytechnic as an active learning strategy for CBET curriculum delivery.
2. Assess the means of access to video learning by the trainers and trainees at Nyandarua National Polytechnic.
3. Identify the challenges faced by the trainers and trainees in Nyandarua National Polytechnic in the employment of video learning as an active learning strategy for CBET curriculum delivery.
4. Establish whether the trainers and trainees in Nyandarua National Polytechnic are adequately equipped to create and use videos for active learning.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Competency-Based Education and Training (CBET)

CBET may be defined in various ways. First of all, it can be defined as training based on the participant's ability to demonstrate mastery of skills performed under certain conditions, to specific standards which he or she must acquire before moving to the next phase of learning or life. The key defining terms in CBET training are skills, knowledge, and attitudes that are central to a career and must be demonstrable. It is beneficial to learners in that it equips learners with skills, knowledge, and attitudes relevant to a particular industry, hence increasing their employability. "CBET curriculum emphasizes action learning. It focuses on what the trainee can do as opposed to what the trainee knows" (Jwan, 2022). Acquisition of demonstrable skills that are actionable is thus a significant aspect of CBET.

Competency-based education and training (CBET) is not a new concept in the world, as it has existed and been applied in many institutions in different parts of the world, as evidenced by a range of published works. In particular, Jwan (2022) has enumerated its adoption in different countries, including Kenya. However, in Kenya, CBET is relatively new as it has been adopted

as a system of learning in the last three years, and mainly in the last one and a half years. Consequently, trainers in TVET institutions have been undergoing related training to build their capacity to implement it. However, the majority of the Kenyan population is unacquainted with the concept, including parents and students joining TVET institutions where it is being offered. This has called for consistent education, sensitization, and awareness creation among all stakeholders in these institutions and the entire citizenry. About the learning process, CBET is beneficial to the learner in that it is learner-centered, improves the trainer-learner relationship, provides for continuous assessment, and keeps learners actively engaged in the learning process. In addition, CBET facilitates career progression while also providing partial certification. CBET can be looked at as a personalized learning experience for each student, where a student moves at his or her own pace to acquire the required competency. Through recognition of prior learning (RPL), trainees also have the benefit of having their prior knowledge recognized and certified, thereby positioning them strategically in the local and international labour market.

2.2 Active learning

Active learning is one of the principles of CBET. It has become the current trend that is taking space from the traditional instructional methods (Hartikainen et al, 2019). It entails learners being engaged in their learning as opposed to the mode where trainers transfer knowledge to learners. Active learning engages students in the process of learning through activities and discussion in class as opposed to passively listening to an expert. Some of the terms that have been used to define active learning include student-centred, opposite of lectures, reflection and thinking, student action, construction of knowledge, collaboration, activating activities, and concrete action in class, among others, which have also been proven to result in positive learning outcomes. Active learning aids learners in understanding as well as constructing their knowledge (Brame, 2016). Evidence from many quarters serves to show that active learning strategies are beneficial to all students as they are learner-centred and enhance inclusivity among other benefits. A large body of recent research supports the role of active learning as a superior approach compared to traditional, more content-centred approaches such as lecturing (Hartikainen et al, 2019). However, implementation of active learning demands additional resources for learner engagement as aptly exemplified by Lombardi & Shipley (2021), “to provide students with active-learning opportunities in the classroom, institutions and professional societies have been developing new infrastructure.” Other studies have also singled out supporting infrastructure as one of the prerequisites for student active learning to succeed (Borte, Nesje & Lillejord, 2020).

2.3 Video learning

The effect of the use of video in learning in terms of learner engagement and an increase in retention rate cannot be overemphasized. Many studies have brought to the fore the benefits of video learning, especially in enhancing learner-centred learning. A study by Learning Technologies Research Group (2014) lists the benefits of video learning, such as promoting learning outcomes, increasing the rate of learner-trainer interaction, and higher levels of learner

satisfaction. Riyanto and Yunani (2020) found the video to be an effective tutorial learning medium with the ability to increase students' abilities. These findings are supported by Puspaningtyas & Ulfa (2020). The benefits of using video to support learning are also espoused by Chan (2010), who notes that when used appropriately, video can be a powerful teaching medium to grab students' attention and can also be a strong motivator for learning. He adds that "using videos as an aid for teaching relieves the instructor of repeating lectures of skilled demonstrations". Video is seen as having advantages for learner engagement in some specific ways, notably in widening participation, emotional engagement, and overall course engagement (Carmichael et al, 2023). Many other empirical studies serve to exemplify the benefits of using video as a tool for learning. Video is therefore an important aid in CBET curriculum implementation and delivery, whose main emphasis is learner-centredness and skills acquisition.

Video use for various purposes has permeated the lives of people in many spheres, including classrooms for teaching and learning, as attested to by Woolfitt (2015). However, its use in learning activities in TVET institutions, despite its benefits, is still unclear, considering that video use also presents some barriers, like challenges with technology. This paper intends to shed some light on this aspect by answering questions like whether the use of video has been embraced by both trainers and trainees in TVET institutions in Kenya as an active learning strategy for CBET implementation, whether the videos used are locally produced or elsewhere sought, whether the videos meet the training needs of trainers and learners and whether the trainers and trainees in TVET institutions are adequately equipped to create and use videos for learning. According to Woolfitt (2015), the pressure to incorporate new technology in teaching and learning is not always matched with adequate training and support. In a related study on the *Applicability of YouTube as a Pedagogical Tool in Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET)*, Wandago et al (2017) allude to the challenges of employing more innovative instructional strategies in TVET institutions.

2.4 Theoretical framework

The study was founded on the following two theories:

Constructivism (Woolfitt, 2015). The theory by Jean Piaget holds that the learning process entails learners' active engagement in the process of constructing relevant knowledge; the more active the involvement, the more the learning potential. Constructivist learning moves from experience to knowledge and not the other way around. Four principles guide it: (i) learners construct their meaning; (ii) new learning builds on prior knowledge; (iii) learning is enhanced by social interaction; and (iv) learning develops through "authentic" tasks (Cooperstein & Kocevar-Weidinger, 2004). The other theory is the Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning (Carmichael et al, 2023). Developed by psychologist Richard Mayer, the theory asserts the importance of the combination of visual and auditory messages in enhancing learner understanding of information presented to him or her in teaching and learning.

3. METHODOLOGY

The study was conducted at Nyandarua National Polytechnic. It was descriptive in design and employed the quantitative approach for data collection and analysis. Data was collected through questionnaires, which were administered online for the trainees and self-administered for the trainers. The response rate of the trainer respondents was 100%, while that of the trainee respondents was 84%. Quantitative data was analyzed using SPSS in the form of frequencies and percentages and presented in tables, graphs, and charts.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following were the main findings of the study:

The majority (60%) of the trainee respondents were mainly from level 6, indicating a high use of video learning among this level of students.

Figure 1.1: Level of study of respondents

Trainers were required to state whether they used video in learning, and the following were their responses:

Table 1.1: Trainers' use of video learning

		Frequency	Per cent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	yes	18	90.0	90.0	90.0
	No	2	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	20	100.0	100.0	

90% of the trainers in the study reported using video in teaching, as demonstrated in the table below. This assertion was corroborated by the trainees' responses, where 88% reported using video learning as seen in Figure 1.2 below.

Figure 1.2: Trainees' use of video learning

It is therefore evident that video learning has been embraced by both trainers and trainees in Nyandarua National Polytechnic. Another question was on the source of the videos used in learning where results indicated that 60% of the videos were online sourced while 18% were locally produced as the graph below indicates.

Figure 1.3: Source of videos used in learning

The high number of online-sourced videos evokes the question of the capacity of trainers in TVET institutions are to create their own teaching and learning videos. Further questions revealed that the locally produced videos were trainer-created, meaning a few trainers could create the videos. Locally created videos are more effective since they are customized to suit the specific content being delivered. They are also relevant to the learning situation and circumstances as opposed to online-sourced videos. Learners are also able to easily identify with the videos and the images presented. (Bull and Bell (2010) have espoused the affordances of teachers or students creating the video for classroom learning.

In terms of access, the smartphone leads in modes of access at 84.2%, followed by the computer, as Figure 1.4 below indicates. This means that video learning can only be done if learners have smartphones and the internet on their phones to employ video learning. This scenario points to a lack of requisite infrastructure for video learning, where trainees can learn without using their smartphones or the trainers’.

Figure 1.4: Means of access to video for learning

Despite the videos being accessed on smartphones, many trainers (64%) affirmed that their video learning was trainer-assisted while 34 % learned on video unassisted as seen in the chart below. Trainer-assisted video learning would be assumed to be common learning in class and therefore a common device like a computer and screen or projector would have been appropriate pointing to a gap in terms of resources and infrastructure.

Figure 1.5: Whether video learning was trainer-assisted or unassisted

When asked about their views on the use of video learning to aid learner participation, the majority of learners stated that video learning aided their participation well, and some thought of it highly.

Figure 1.6: Views of learners on video learning in aiding participation

This finding confirms the many already documented benefits of video learning in aiding learner participation and skills acquisition. This means that employing video learning as one of the digital technologies in TVET institutions will transform the mode of learning in these institutions to more innovative learning strategies, with the results of equipping the trainees with their relevant skills for increased employability. Also worth noting is the fact that the application of digital tools in teaching and learning in TVET institutions serves to improve individual users' digital skills in general, even for application in other sectors of life and work. This again improves the functioning of TVET graduates in the industry, which has already greatly embraced digital technology through digitalization and automation of many processes and operations.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The study concludes that adopting video learning in TVET institutions has the potential to transform traditional teaching methods, enhance skills acquisition among graduates, and improve employability. Furthermore, video learning has been embraced by TVET institutions as a strategy for promoting active learning. Another conclusion from the study is that TVET institutions in Kenya have embraced video learning as an active learning strategy, going by the case of Nyandarua National Polytechnic. However, despite the embrace, video learning is being faced with myriad challenges, particularly a lack of requisite resources and infrastructure for access and creation of videos for learning. Trainers and trainees are also not adequately skilled to effectively apply this innovative digital learning tool.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. TVET institutions in Kenya should embrace video learning as one of the digital technologies for teaching and learning to enhance skills acquisition and employability among TVET graduates.
2. TVET institutions in Kenya should provide adequate resources and infrastructure for the employment of innovative digital teaching and learning technologies for CBET implementation.
3. Trainers in TVET institutions should be equipped with the requisite skills to create and use video in CBET curriculum delivery.

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